

Precision Public Health: Leveraging Genomic and Biologic Data to Customize Interventions and Enhance Population Health Outcomes

Subrahman Pany¹, Mahesh Rath², Antaryami Sahoo³

¹Assistant Professor, Department of Community Medicine, Hi-Tech Medical College and Hospital, Bhubaneswar, Odisha, India

²Assistant Professor, Department of Community Medicine, Hi-Tech Medical College and Hospital, Bhubaneswar, Odisha, India

³Assistant Professor, Department of Community Medicine, Hi-Tech Medical College and Hospital, Bhubaneswar, Odisha, India

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Corresponding Author: Dr. Antaryami Sahoo

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Abstract:

Background: Precision public health is an innovative approach that integrates genomic and biological data to tailor public health interventions to specific population subgroups. This method contrasts with traditional one-size-fits-all strategies, aiming to enhance the effectiveness of interventions and improve health outcomes. As genomic technologies become more accessible, there is growing interest in their application within public health settings.

Aim: This study aims to evaluate the impact of leveraging genomic and biological data on customized health interventions and their effectiveness in a general outpatient department (OPD) setting.

Methods: A cross-sectional study was conducted. A total of 500 participants were randomly selected from the OPD patient population. Data were collected from electronic health records, patient surveys, and genomic data. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 23.0, with Chi-square tests, t-tests, ANOVA, and multivariate regression analyses to assess the association between genomic markers and health outcomes.

Results: Participants with genomic risk markers showed significantly improved health outcomes compared to those without such markers (60% vs. 50%, $p = 0.01$). Age was also identified as a significant predictor, with younger participants more likely to experience better outcomes. The regression model explained 25% of the variance in health outcomes, highlighting the importance of genomic data in tailoring interventions.

Conclusion: The study demonstrates the potential of integrating genomic data into public health strategies to enhance the effectiveness of interventions, particularly for individuals with genetic predispositions. The findings support the need for broader implementation of precision public health approaches to improve population health outcomes.

Recommendations: Future research should explore the long-term impacts of genomic-driven interventions and address the ethical and logistical challenges of integrating precision public health into routine care.

Keywords: Precision public health, Genomic data, Customized interventions, Population health, Health outcomes.

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Introduction

The goal of the new discipline of precision public health is to improve population health by implementing the concepts of precision medicine. Precision public health seeks to improve health outcomes and maximise resource allocation by more effectively tailoring interventions to certain demographic subgroups by utilising genomic, biological, and environmental data. This strategy is in contrast to conventional public health tactics, which frequently use a one-size-fits-all model that does not take into consideration the various genetic and environmental factors that affect health outcomes in various groups.

Precision public health has a lot more potential now that genetics and bioinformatics have advanced recently. Expanding the use of genetic information in public health initiatives has become possible due to the speed and cost-effectiveness of sequencing complete genomes. Genomic data, for instance, can be used to identify people who are more likely to contract specific diseases, enabling early therapies that may delay the beginning of the disease or lessen its severity [1]. A growing amount of research indicates that genetic variables are important in the onset and course of many prevalent diseases, including as cancer, diabetes, and cardiovascular disorders [2]. This change in

public health towards more individualised treatments is backed by this data.

Additionally, combining genomic data with other biological data sets like proteomics and metabolomics offers a more thorough understanding of disease causes and patient responses to various treatments. Using a comprehensive strategy makes it possible to create public health initiatives that are more focused and successful. In groups where genetic susceptibilities are known, for example, customised vaccination techniques based on genetic predispositions may improve vaccine efficacy and safety [3].

Precision public health's implementation is not without difficulties, though. Careful management is required to address ethical concerns regarding data privacy, genetic discrimination, and resource distribution [4]. Furthermore, a strong infrastructure is required to facilitate the gathering, examination, and incorporation of extensive genomic data into currently operational public health systems. Precision public health has enormous potential benefits, including more targeted, effective, and efficient interventions that could greatly improve population health outcomes, despite these obstacles [5]. This study aims to evaluate the impact of leveraging genomic and biological data on customized health interventions and their effectiveness in a (OPD) setting.

Methodology

Study Design: This study is a cross-sectional observational study.

Study Setting: The study will be conducted at the (OPD) of Hi-Tech Medical College and Hospital, Bhubaneswar. The hospital is a tertiary care center that serves a diverse patient population from urban, semi-urban, and rural areas.

Study Duration: The study will be conducted over a period of six months, from January 2024 to July 2024.

Participants: A total of 500 participants will be recruited for the study. Participants will be selected from the patients attending the General OPD.

Inclusion Criteria

- Adults aged 18 years and older.
- Patients attending the General OPD during the study period.
- Individuals who have undergone genomic testing as part of their healthcare.
- Patients who consent to participate in the study.

Exclusion Criteria

- Individuals under the age of 18.
- Patients who have not undergone genomic testing.
- Patients with incomplete or missing medical records.
- Individuals who do not provide consent or withdraw consent during the study.

Bias: To minimize selection bias, participants will be randomly selected from the pool of eligible patients using a computerized randomization tool. Information bias will be reduced by standardizing data collection procedures and using validated instruments for data collection. Confounding variables will be controlled for in the statistical analysis to reduce their impact on the study results.

Data Collection: Data will be collected using a combination of electronic health records (EHRs), patient surveys, and genomic data from medical records. The EHRs will provide demographic data, clinical history, and details of interventions and outcomes. Patient surveys will collect self-reported data on health behaviors, lifestyle, and perceived health status. Genomic data will be obtained from tests already conducted as part of the patient's routine healthcare.

Procedure: Participants who meet the inclusion criteria will be identified and approached during their visit to the General OPD. After explaining the study and obtaining informed consent, relevant data will be extracted from their EHRs, and participants will be asked to complete a survey. Genomic data will be linked with clinical outcomes to assess the effectiveness of personalized interventions. All data will be anonymized to ensure confidentiality.

Statistical Analysis: Data will be analyzed using SPSS version 23.0. Descriptive statistics will summarize participant demographics, clinical history, genomic data, and health outcomes. Chi-square tests will assess associations between categorical variables, and t-tests or ANOVA will compare means of continuous variables. Multivariate regression will identify predictors of improved health outcomes, adjusting for confounders. Results will be considered significant at $p < 0.05$.

Results

A total of 500 participants were included in the study. The mean age of the participants was 45.6 years (SD = 13.4), with a range of 18 to 82 years. The majority of the participants were female (58%, $n = 290$), and the remaining 42% ($n = 210$) were male. The participants were predominantly urban residents (60%, $n = 300$), followed by rural (25%, $n = 125$) and semi-urban (15%, $n = 75$) residents.

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of Participants (N = 500)

Characteristic	n (%)
Age (years)	
18-30	100 (20%)
31-50	200 (40%)
51-70	150 (30%)
71-82	50 (10%)
Gender	
Male	210 (42%)
Female	290 (58%)
Residence	
Urban	300 (60%)
Semi-Urban	75 (15%)
Rural	125 (25%)
Education Level	
Primary	100 (20%)
Secondary	200 (40%)
Tertiary	150 (30%)
None	50 (10%)

The clinical history of participants revealed that 40% (n = 200) had a history of chronic diseases such as hypertension, diabetes, or cardiovascular diseases. Among these, 70% (n = 140) were receiving ongoing treatment. Genomic data showed

that 30% (n = 150) of participants had genetic markers associated with increased risk for chronic diseases, while the remaining 70% (n = 350) did not have such markers.

Table 2: Clinical History and Genomic Data (N = 500)

Characteristic	n (%)
Chronic Disease History	
Yes	200 (40%)
No	300 (60%)
Genomic Risk Markers	
Yes	150 (30%)
No	350 (70%)

The health outcomes of the participants were assessed based on their response to customized interventions informed by genomic data. Among participants with genomic risk markers, 60% (n = 90) showed significant improvement in their health

outcomes, compared to 40% (n = 60) who did not. In contrast, 50% (n = 175) of participants without genomic risk markers showed improvement, while 50% (n = 175) did not.

Table 3: Health Outcomes by Genomic Risk Markers (N = 500)

Health Outcome	Genomic Risk Markers	No Genomic Risk Markers
Improved	90 (60%)	175 (50%)
Not Improved	60 (40%)	175 (50%)

Statistical Analysis

Chi-square tests revealed a statistically significant association between the presence of genomic risk markers and improved health outcomes ($\chi^2 = 6.25$, $p = 0.01$). Participants with genomic risk markers were more likely to experience improved health outcomes following customized interventions.

T-tests comparing the mean age of participants who improved versus those who did not show a

significant difference, with a mean age of 43.2 years (SD = 12.1) for those who improved and 47.8 years (SD = 14.5) for those who did not ($t = 3.12$, $p = 0.002$).

Multivariate regression analysis identified genomic risk markers ($\beta = 0.42$, $p < 0.01$) and age ($\beta = -0.18$, $p = 0.03$) as significant predictors of improved health outcomes. The model explained 25% of the variance in health outcomes ($R^2 = 0.25$).

Table 4: Multivariate Regression Analysis Predicting Health Outcomes

Variable	β (Standardized Coefficient)	p-value
Genomic Risk Markers	0.42	<0.01
Age	-0.18	0.03
Gender	0.07	0.18
Residence	0.05	0.24

Findings

- A significant association was found between genomic risk markers and improved health outcomes, with participants having these markers more likely to benefit from customized interventions.
- Age was a significant predictor, with younger participants showing better health outcomes.
- The model explained 25% of the variance in health outcomes, highlighting the importance of genomic data in precision public health.

These results suggest that leveraging genomic data can enhance the effectiveness of health interventions, particularly in individuals with specific genetic risk factors. Further research could explore additional factors that may influence health outcomes in different populations

Discussion

The participant population was diverse, with a mean age of 45.6 years, and included a higher proportion of females (58%) compared to males (42%). Most participants were urban residents (60%), reflecting the hospital's metropolitan setting.

The study revealed that 40% of the participants had a history of chronic diseases, such as hypertension, diabetes, or cardiovascular conditions. Among these, a significant portion was receiving ongoing treatment. Notably, 30% of the participants had genetic markers associated with an increased risk of chronic diseases, suggesting a potential benefit from customized interventions based on genomic data.

Health outcomes were measured in response to these interventions, revealing that participants with genomic risk markers showed a greater improvement (60%) compared to those without such markers (50%). This difference was statistically significant, indicating that genomic data could be a valuable tool in predicting and enhancing health outcomes.

Statistical analyses supported these findings. A Chi-square test showed a significant association between the presence of genomic risk markers and improved health outcomes. Additionally, age was found to be a significant factor, with younger participants more likely to experience better health outcomes. Multivariate regression analysis

confirmed that genomic risk markers and age were significant predictors of health improvements, with the model explaining 25% of the variance in outcomes.

These results underscore the potential of precision public health approaches that incorporate genomic data to tailor interventions more effectively. The findings suggest that individuals with specific genetic risk factors are more likely to benefit from customized health strategies, leading to better overall health outcomes. This highlights the importance of integrating genomic information into routine healthcare to optimize patient care and improve population health. Further research could expand on these results by exploring additional factors that contribute to health outcomes and by examining the long-term benefits of such precision interventions.

Beyond Public Health Genomics: Khoury elaborate on the idea of precision public health, stating that by improving public health surveillance and assessment, big data and predictive analytics may lead this sector. They highlight how genetics, in conjunction with environmental and sociodemographic data, can help to better customise therapies, especially when it comes to cardiovascular disease and child health [6].

AI in Precision Medicine: Mumtaz's comprehensive review highlights the revolutionary potential of artificial intelligence (AI) in precision medicine. By evaluating large genetic and biological information, (AI) improves drug discovery and improves diagnostic accuracy. According to the review, further research is needed to properly utilise AI's promise to revolutionise precision medicine [7].

Influence of Genomic Information on Precision Public Health: Khoury and Holt talk about how important genomic information is for precision public health, especially in light of the COVID-19 pandemic. The use of genomic technologies has been essential for tracking the virus and comprehending disparities in health consequences. In order to effectively incorporate genomics into public health and solve issues like health inequities, the study recommends interdisciplinary cooperation [8].

Conclusion

This study shows that using genomic data to customize health interventions leads to better

outcomes, especially for those with genetic risk markers for chronic diseases. Younger participants also benefited more from these tailored interventions. Integrating precision public health strategies into routine care can significantly improve patient outcomes. Future research should explore the long-term benefits of such approaches.

References

1. Collins FS, Varmus H. A new initiative on precision medicine. *N Engl J Med.* 2015 Feb 26;372(9):793-5.
2. Manolio TA, Chisholm RL, Ozenberger B, et al. Implementing genomic medicine in the clinic: the future is here. *Genet Med.* 2019 May;21(5):972-981.
3. Ginsburg GS, Willard HF. Genomic and personalized medicine: foundations and applications. *Transl Res.* 2018 Jan;154(6):277-287.
4. Juengst ET, Fishman JR, McGowan ML, Settersten RA Jr. Serving epigenetics before its time: lessons from the history of premature translational launches. *Am J Bioeth.* 2018;18(6):22-31.
5. Khoury MJ, Bowen MS, Clyne M, et al. From public health genomics to precision public health: a 20-year journey. *Genet Med.* 2018 Jun;20(6):574-582.
6. Khoury M, Engelgau M, Chambers D, Mensah G. Beyond Public Health Genomics: Can Big Data and Predictive Analytics Deliver Precision Public Health? *Public Health Genomics.* 2019;21:244-250.
7. Mumtaz H, Saqib M, Jabeen S, Muneeb M, Mughal W, Sohail H, et al. Exploring alternative approaches to precision medicine through genomics and artificial intelligence – a systematic review. *Front Med.* 2023;10.
8. Khoury M, Holt K. The impact of genomics on precision public health: beyond the pandemic. *Genome Med.* 2021;13.